

TRANSITIONS PATHWAYS AND RISK ANALYSIS FOR CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION STRATEGIES

D7.3: Toolboxes for adaptation and mitigation policy pathways

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Preface

Both the models concerning the future climate evolution and its impacts, as well as the models assessing the costs and benefits associated with different mitigation pathways face a high degree of uncertainty. There is an urgent need to not only understand the *costs and benefits* associated with *climate change* but also the *risks, uncertainties and co-effects* related to different *mitigation pathways* as well as *public acceptance* (or lack of) of low-carbon (technology) options. The main aims and objectives of TRANSrisk therefore are to create a novel assessment framework for analysing costs and benefits of transition pathways that will integrate well-established approaches to modelling the costs of resilient, low-carbon pathways with a wider interdisciplinary approach including risk assessments. In addition *TRANSrisk* aims to design a decision support tool that should help policy makers to better understand uncertainties and risks and enable them to include risk assessments into more robust policy design.

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Executive Summary

Policymaking under deep uncertainty implies policymakers will encounter difficulties when asked to design and implement a new policy. Predicting the future, and deciding on the most probable evolution before applying a policy, has often been unsuccessful, thus the notion of adaptive policies has emerged. By adaptive policies we mean those that focus on short-term planning, and present a robust framework of potential adjustive interventions to choose from when the initial policy is no longer expected to lead to success.

Furthermore, within complex systems where environmental policies affect metrics in other sectors, policymaking has become harder, even for the short-term planning. In this report two toolboxes - an adaptation and a mitigation policy toolbox - capable of addressing these aforementioned problems and facilitating robust and successful policymaking are presented.

The central concept of the adaptation toolbox is to allow stakeholders to design adaptive policies, meaning to focus on short-term policy actions followed by a set of adaptive interventions. It produces intuitive visualisations of alternative pathways (adaptation maps - mixture of policies) leading to a desired target, by evaluating a large number of scenarios, created by diverse stakeholders' perspectives acquired through large-scale consultation.

The basic functionality of the adaptation toolbox is based on the notion of model-emulation, by which a statistical model is trained using sets of inputs and outputs produced by a (heavy) model. The resulting emulator can consequently be used for fast and accurate model estimations. This is achieved using a Gaussian Process-based machine learning algorithm achieving:

- (i) Fast/interactive model approximations, which help establish a tight loop between stakeholders and the modelling teams. This makes it possible to identify options and scenarios in a timely fashion that stakeholders either reject or explore further in terms of costs or impacts.
- (ii) Quantification of the uncertainties governing the modelling assumptions, through the relevance-based learning capability of the adaptation toolbox, with which users can evaluate what the most valuable data for the given task are.

To produce adaptation maps, the adaptation toolbox performs a “cause and effect” analysis to identify triggers that signpost imminent deviations from the set targets. This is done using the Patient Rule Induction Method (PRIM), clustering algorithm which identifies parameters that caused the success or failure of a specific policy instrument.

To present the above functionalities, emulation of a heavy bottom-up model for the case of Greece has been performed using randomly generated scenarios. The randomness of the scenarios simulates the diverse perspectives that stakeholders might have, and stress test the accuracy of the toolbox. An adaptation map is produced, and two sample pathways are generated according to two different hypothetical perspectives.

The emulation results show that the output parameter trend is correctly predicted by the emulator. More importantly, the estimation of results required only 0.2 seconds of execution time per 10-year scenario, while the per 10-year scenario execution time in the original, bottom-up model was 4 hours. These two observations reveal the capabilities of the adaptation toolbox to produce quick and accurate simulation results.

The main idea behind the mitigation toolbox is to enable policy makers who are not experts in the field of macroeconomic modelling to run basic country level simulations of climate change mitigation policies. This is done through embedding macroeconomic models in a web-based application with an intuitive graphical user interface. Use of the toolbox does not require any programming or technical skills, the user must only select one of the predefined simulation types and provide input data.

Currently, the application is equipped with macroeconomic models for Chile, Greece and Poland and allows simulation of policies such as environmental taxes, expansion plans in the electricity generation sector and sector specific mitigation actions, including changes in use of various fuels and products by the household. Thanks to the toolbox policy makers will be able to quickly obtain an initial assessment of the macroeconomic consequences of their proposed policies without the need to engage economists to perform the simulations.

The toolbox provides results for basic macroeconomic and sector indicators such as gross domestic product, investment, employment, unemployment, wages, foreign trade as well as emissions of carbon dioxide. In order to facilitate learning of the use of the toolbox, sample simulations for a decarbonisation intervention (CO₂ emissions must be reduced by 60% relative to the 2018 levels until 2050) in the energy sector for Poland is provided. The main stand out result of the simulation is the increase in total investment in the economy, which is due to the increased investment in the energy sector. However, this increase crowds out investment in other sectors of the economy; this contributes to a slight fall in GDP and employment, and a much larger decrease of private consumption.

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1 EC SUMMARY REQUIREMENTS

1.1 Changes with respect to the DoA

There are no changes with respect to the DoA.

1.2 Dissemination and uptake

This Deliverable and its associated tools can be used by policy makers to aid the formulation of effective climate policy. It can also be used by other interested parties, such as consultants and NGOs, to explore the impact of climate policies and to inform development of their own policy proposals.

1.3 Short Summary of results (<250 words)

Classic decision making used to be based on a static plan considered optimal for the “most likely” future outcome. This strategy has proven vulnerable to unexpected future evolutions, which lead to failure of the plan once considered optimal. This is why the concept of dynamic, adaptive policies, which focuses on short-term planning and describe potential future adaptive actions, has emerged in the past few years. This Deliverable presents two toolboxes to assist with such a policy process - one for adaptation policies and one for mitigation.

The first tool, STEEM, is a model emulator for use with adaptive policies. By training the emulator with the inputs and outputs of traditional, computational intensive models, STEEM is able to make quick approximations of the impacts of policy decisions, and provide outputs in a visual format. STEEM is particularly suited for use in iterative, stakeholder driven processes, as it can provide quick feedback to stakeholders on the impacts of their policy choices.

The second tool, MEMO is a large-scale Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium model. In this case it has been developed as an easy to use web application to allow non-experts to conduct macro-economic simulations of various policies. Use of the MEMO tool can speed up and expand policy development by allowing the policy community to run multiple ‘what if?’ scenarios on their own desktops, rather than having to involve dedicated modelling teams every time a variable is changed.

1.4 Evidence of accomplishment

This Deliverable and the accompanying tools.

2 INTRODUCTION

Climate policymaking is a complex process, characterised by deep uncertainties and continuous changes in both the parameters and external factors (i.e. technological innovation, social behaviour, economic development etc.) affecting the dynamics of the energy system (Haasnoot, Kwakkel, Walker, & ter Maat, 2013). Decisionmakers, in their effort to create robust policies, can find themselves confused or incapable of making proper decisions, often due to insufficient information about the uncertainties they need to consider (Forni, et al., 2016).

Classic decision making used to be based on a static plan considered optimal for the “most likely” future outcome. This strategy has proven vulnerable to unexpected future evolutions, which lead to failure of the plan once considered optimal. This is why the concept of dynamic, adaptive policies, which focuses on short-term planning and describe potential future adaptive actions, has emerged in the past few years (Haasnoot, Kwakkel, Walker, & ter Maat, 2013). Furthermore, nowadays multiple (usually contradictory) objectives have to be met in different sectors. The respective policies often interact with each other, either in a positive or negative manner, posing implementation barriers for each other (Michas, et al., 2018).

Investigating the effects of a specific policy instrument in multiple sectors is therefore an important inquiry, and would be useful for policymakers to consider before the application of a new policy. These investigations can be aided by modelling software, capable of simulating multiple parameters, sectors and contexts, resulting in the generation of multiple energy transition scenarios. These, in turn, can be translated into energy and climate policies. However, the main drawback of modelling exercises is their vulnerability to parameter uncertainties which can lead to false simulation results (Enserink, Kwakkel, & Veenman, 2013).

In the context of Deliverable 7.3, we present two models capable of tackling the aforementioned policymaking difficulties namely: (i) quantification of uncertainty and design of adaptive policies and; (ii) multisectoral evaluation of policy outcomes. The respective models are the STatistical approximation-based modEL EMulator (STEEM - adaptation toolbox) and the MacroEconomic Mitigations Options model (MEMO - mitigation toolbox).

- STEEM is a model-agnostic, data-driven framework, emulating the operation of usually heavy (i.e. bottom-up) models in a much quicker and more computational efficient fashion. Furthermore, through its relevance-based capability, STEEM quantifies the uncertainties governing the modelling assumptions, thus enabling users to identify the most influential data to the given task. Finally, STEEM visualises a policy adaptation map, showing alternative pathways leading to a desired policy outcome, which can be used by a policymaker to design adaptive policies. These capabilities make STEEM an appropriate tool for incorporating multiple stakeholders’ perspectives into modelling scenarios, and performing quick simulations as part of an iterative participatory process that aims to solve complex problems with high levels of uncertainty (Forni, et al., 2016).

- MEMO is a large-scale Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium model, developed as a web application to allow non-experts to conduct macro-economic simulations of various policies. Users can select one of the predefined simulation types to perform simulations for three countries, each one with a built-in macro-economic model. The results from MEMO can be used to assess the effect of various interventions related to climate change mitigation on a range of macroeconomic indicators, such as gross domestic product, added value, employment, wages, exports, imports, tax revenue and others, on an aggregate and sector level.

The two models are analytically presented in the sections 3 and 4 of the Deliverable respectively. Each section initiates with a brief description of the model, continues with analytical usage details and input requirements and concludes with simulations applied on a TRANSrisk case study. Also, some semi-technical details of the models are provided.

3 TOOLBOX FOR ADAPTATION POLICY PATHWAYS USING THE STEEM MODEL EMULATOR

3.1 Introduction

Energy transition efforts across the world often face significant uncertainties around subjects such as energy planning and policy mixes, which will allow for a sustainable and supply-secure decarbonisation of the energy sector (Chappin, et al., 2017; Pfenninger, et al., 2018). Purposeful modelling practices can play a pivotal role, both in highlighting sustainable transition pathways and in building consensus between decision-makers and the modelling communities (Doukas, 2013).

Energy models have proven to be one of the key tools in understanding the dynamics of energy systems. They allow simulation of potential electricity generation mixes, guiding policies supporting the penetration of specific generation technologies that constitute an optimal electricity generation configuration. Assessment of the various generation technologies, and their effect on specific metrics, is a difficult task which has been significantly facilitated by the use of energy models (Müller, Gardumi, & Hülk, 2018; Pfenninger, et al., 2018).

However, modelling exercises often face the problems of computational complexity, which can lead to time-consuming simulations. When modelling a problem with multiple variables, significant resolution and modelling depth is required to assess the various aspects of the problem. Each of these aspects are usually characterised by high-order non-linearity and complexity, making them computationally-intensive and time-consuming to simulate. While resolving each aspect in depth enables a significant level of detail to be achieved, modelling all aspects of a problem (and their intertwinement) may result in unacceptable computational and time demands (Chappin, et al., 2017; Pfenninger, et al., 2018; Qiu, Li, Pang, Zhang, & Li, 2018).

One possible solution growing in popularity is a so-called “black-box” modelling approach, which is a data-driven modelling technique. Outputs are mapped to inputs and used to train a statistical model. This approach provides ‘approximate’ outputs, without the need to know (and calculate) the analytical engineering dynamics and mathematical landscape governing the exact model (Yoon & Moon, 2018). Such models, once calibrated, are used to simulate complex problems much more efficiently in terms of computational and time resources (Yuan, Nian, & Su, 2017).

In the context of Task 7.3, a model-agnostic “black-box” framework, the Statistical approximation-based model EMulator (STEEM), has been developed as a toolbox to facilitate fast model approximations. The major contributions of the STEEM platform, in the context of both TRANSrisk and the wider modelling community, are as follows:

- Fast/interactive model approximations. This can help establish a tight loop between stakeholders and the modelling teams, thus making it possible to identify options and scenarios in a timely fashion that stakeholders either reject or explore further in terms of costs or impacts.
- Quantification of the uncertainties governing the modelling assumptions. Through the relevance-based learning capability of the STEEM, users can evaluate what the most valuable data for the given task are.

While many studies have been performed on the “black-box” mode (Heo & Zavala, 2012; Massa Gray & Schmidt, 2016; Shepero, van der Meer, Munkhammar, & Widén, 2018), each of them focused on a specific problem, thus posing them difficult to apply to other studies. The main innovation of STEEM is that it has been developed in a model-agnostic way, where every potential user (from modellers to stakeholders) can use it and derive quick results according to his/her needs.

The following sections present an analysis of STEEM’s structure and operation, and its practical application to TRANSrisk’s Greek case study.

3.2 The “black box” emulator

Following Müller et al. (2018), we should first make a distinction between models and frameworks.

- A framework is a mathematical representation of the approach used to address a problem, and is used to build a model.
- A model is the application of the framework, after its refinement to account for the specificities of the problem’s context (i.e. regional specificities, technologies under assessment etc.).

Using this definition, STEEM belongs to the framework family - it uses a purely mathematical methodology to emulate the operation of analytical, computationally-complex models, but without the requirement to know the dynamics, physics, engineering, etc. governing these models. This justifies the term “model-agnostic”, which is adopted to characterize its independent nature. However, how does the emulator map outputs to inputs without knowing the underlying mathematics?

To completely characterise the emulator and at the same time answer the above question, we need one more set of definitions. For this, we followed Reynolds et al. (2018) to assign models (as well as frameworks) to white box, grey box and black box definitions, depending on the mechanics used for their operation.

- White box models are those utilising analytical engineering, physics etc. principles to simulate the operation of systems. These models usually require a great amount of input data and

sufficient computational power to calculate outputs. They can achieve a significant level of simulation accuracy.

- Grey box models use simplified mathematical representations of the problem in conjunction with parameter approximation techniques to determine the final functional forms. These models require less computational resources at the expense to a lower level of accuracy.
- Black box models are ignorant of the underlying mathematics. They need a two-step approach to use them. The first step is called calibration: inputs and outputs produced from the analytical models, or based on historical data, are given to the model to train it. Then, the trained model is used to make approximations/predictions, emulating the original model behind the data. Statistical regressions, neural networks and other machine learning methodologies are most often used to train the model and produce approximations. The main advantage of these models is the low computational requirements and consequently the fast simulations.

STEEM belongs to the black box category and uses a Gaussian Process (GP) regression (see section 3.5) for the calibration and prediction procedures.

3.3 Emulating BSAM for the case study of Greece

3.3.1 STEEM calibration

STEEM's functionality (in terms of results accuracy and reduced computational time requirements), has been validated by emulating the operation of the BSAM (Business Strategy Assessment Model) model. The BSAM model simulates the workings of a complex wholesale day-ahead bidding electricity market and the behaviour of the agents participating in the market. It models, using a per-hour resolution, across a specified period that can span decades:

- The bidding procedure on the day-ahead wholesale market.
- The behaviour of the electricity producers, who aim to maximize profits within a dynamic market.
- The daily electricity market clearance based on the demand, the available power and the costs.

and provides the following outputs in an hourly resolution:

- For each electricity producer: the power produced, costs and profits (defined as income from energy produced minus the variable cost of producing this energy).
- The system marginal price over the modelled period.

- The optimal electricity mix in order to economically match the demand over the modelled period.
- Any other market related metric resulting from the post-processing of the above outputs.

As previously mentioned, STEEM's training requires a set of inputs and outputs from the original model. 25 scenarios for renewable energy sources (RES) uptake were run using the BSAM, 19 of which were used for the calibration (training) procedure, and the remaining 6 for testing the accuracy of STEEM. In this case study, the BSAM has been used to model different scenarios of RES uptake in Greece, and their effect on the electricity mix, the System Marginal Price (SMP) and the total electricity costs (including RES subsidies). From the scenario set, 15 scenarios were run for the period 2015-2020, and 10 scenarios for the period 2015-2025.

In particular, the inputs that were differentiated in each scenario are exactly:

- The annual solar PV capacity growth relatively to 2016 levels
- The annual onshore wind plant capacity growth relatively to 2016 levels
- The percentile availability (of the maximum import capacity) of electricity imports from the interconnected countries¹
- The percentage of solar parks (of the total rooftop and solar park installations)
- Electricity demand data
- Solar PV subsidies (as a percentage of the SMP)
- Onshore wind subsidy (as a fixed tariff)

Table 1 and Table 2 present the scenarios used for the short-term (2015-2020) and medium-term (2015-2025) scenarios respectively.

¹ Albania, Bulgaria, Italy, Republic of North Macedonia, Turkey

Table 1 Inputs of the short-term scenarios run in BSAM

Input Parameter	Year	SC1	SC2	SC3	SC4	SC5	SC6	SC7	SC8	SC9	SC10	SC11	SC12	SC13	SC14	SC15
Annual Solar Growth (relative to 2016 values)	2015	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2016	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2017	1.31	1.36	1.21	1.27	1.23	1.28	1.35	1.38	1.25	1.33	1.69	1.61	1.57	1.66	1.79
	2018	1.59	1.60	1.75	1.48	1.47	1.70	1.64	1.76	1.4	1.54	2.04	2.28	2.32	1.9	2.21
	2019	1.91	1.85	1.97	2.07	2.08	2.14	1.81	2.03	2.19	1.95	2.85	2.92	2.76	2.72	2.63
	2020	2.52	2.50	2.3	2.27	2.38	2.57	2.23	2.47	2.41	2.32	3.29	3.44	3.05	3.6	3.34
Annual Wind Onshore Growth (relative to 2016 values)	2015	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2016	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2017	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.02	1.01	1.02	1.02	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.04	1.05	1.02	1.03	1.02
	2018	1.06	1.05	1.03	1.05	1.04	1.03	1.06	1.03	1.05	1.04	1.13	1.09	1.09	1.11	1.08
	2019	1.08	1.07	1.09	1.09	1.08	1.07	1.09	1.07	1.07	1.08	1.17	1.14	1.19	1.14	1.19
	2020	1.1	1.12	1.12	1.11	1.1	1.12	1.10	1.11	1.11	1.11	1.21	1.23	1.22	1.23	1.2
Imports Availability	2015	1	1.00	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2016	0.87	0.88	0.63	0.78	0.96	0.66	0.81	0.74	0.94	0.68	0.61	0.95	0.66	0.85	0.91
	2017	0.73	0.91	0.86	0.61	0.82	0.7	0.97	0.65	0.78	0.92	0.82	0.69	0.88	0.98	0.63

Input Parameter	Year	SC1	SC2	SC3	SC4	SC5	SC6	SC7	SC8	SC9	SC10	SC11	SC12	SC13	SC14	SC15
	2018	0.85	0.91	0.83	0.98	0.67	0.69	0.62	0.79	0.74	0.94	0.65	0.95	0.7	0.89	0.83
	2019	0.84	0.90	0.82	0.61	0.74	0.71	0.67	0.97	0.93	0.77	0.93	0.77	0.64	0.68	0.91
	2020	0.62	0.99	0.94	0.84	0.81	0.76	0.64	0.88	0.71	0.73	0.82	0.99	0.69	0.63	0.76
% Solar Parks	2015-2020	0.85	0.76	0.53	0.55	0.79	0.64	0.61	0.73	0.69	0.89	0.83	0.80	0.74	0.86	0.67
Demand Scenario	2015-2020	low	low	high	low	high	high	high	low	low	high	high	low	high	low	low
Solar Subsidy (percentage to SMP)	2015-2020	1.01	1.10	1.25	1.2	1.15	1.27	1.03	1.06	1.23	1.12	1.19	1.17	1.24	1.07	1.22
Wind onshore subsidy (€/MWh)	2015-2020	75	83.02	72.81	52.62	86.5	68.19	80.88	62.95	56.09	60.33	52.2	84.20	79.54	76.34	61.02

Table 2 Inputs of the medium-term scenarios run in BSAM

Input Parameter	Year	SC1	SC2	SC3	SC4	SC5	SC6	SC7	SC8	SC9	SC10
Annual Solar Growth (relative to 2016 values)	2015	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2016	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2017	1.25	1.30	1.24	1.39	1.35	1.67	1.74	1.72	1.54	1.56
	2018	1.40	1.78	1.56	1.67	1.56	2.38	1.89	2.23	2.06	2.17
	2019	2.13	2.12	1.97	1.85	1.96	2.90	2.88	2.75	2.54	2.64
	2020	2.54	2.21	2.44	2.41	2.33	3.28	3.52	3.78	3.12	3.45
	2021	2.65	3.00	2.96	2.71	2.87	4.23	3.87	4.2	4.04	4.48
	2022	3.49	3.35	3.23	3.67	3.14	5.38	4.86	5.05	4.56	5.17
	2023	3.80	3.74	4.03	3.93	4.15	6.37	6.68	5.58	5.74	6.1
	2024	4.27	5.08	4.59	4.83	5.39	6.77	7.07	7.84	7.49	7.19
2025	6.42	5.65	5.61	6.15	6.01	8.73	8.37	8.89	9.24	7.93	
Annual Wind Onshore Growth (relative to 2016 values)	2015	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2016	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2017	1.02	1.02	1.03	1.01	1.02	1.03	1.05	1.03	1.02	1.04
	2018	1.03	1.04	1.05	1.06	1.07	1.06	1.08	1.1	1.13	1.11
	2019	1.1	1.07	1.09	1.08	1.09	1.15	1.14	1.18	1.17	1.19
	2020	1.13	1.11	1.11	1.12	1.11	1.24	1.23	1.2	1.22	1.25
	2021	1.14	1.15	1.13	1.14	1.14	1.26	1.28	1.26	1.28	1.29
	2022	1.16	1.16	1.15	1.16	1.17	1.31	1.32	1.33	1.31	1.3
	2023	1.18	1.19	1.17	1.2	1.19	1.38	1.38	1.34	1.35	1.37
	2024	1.22	1.21	1.2	1.22	1.22	1.4	1.44	1.44	1.42	1.41
2025	1.26	1.25	1.24	1.27	1.23	1.51	1.50	1.47	1.53	1.46	
Imports Availability	2015	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2016	0.85	0.79	0.93	0.68	0.64	0.87	0.92	0.8	0.74	0.62
	2017	0.97	0.68	0.69	0.78	0.88	0.74	0.92	0.64	0.86	0.81
	2018	0.73	0.84	0.96	0.89	0.67	0.81	0.62	0.96	0.85	0.75

Input Parameter	Year	SC1	SC2	SC3	SC4	SC5	SC6	SC7	SC8	SC9	SC10
	2019	0.72	0.95	0.65	0.88	0.78	0.97	0.76	0.68	0.89	0.61
	2020	0.83	0.64	0.69	0.9	0.92	0.89	0.74	0.79	0.65	0.97
	2021	0.73	0.99	0.64	0.88	0.81	0.61	0.82	0.92	0.86	0.69
	2022	0.96	0.86	0.67	0.82	0.69	0.81	0.72	0.98	0.89	0.67
	2023	0.73	0.98	0.85	0.78	0.6	0.88	0.72	0.62	0.99	0.76
	2024	0.77	0.72	0.87	0.67	0.97	0.65	0.70	0.99	0.82	0.91
	2025	0.64	0.78	0.7	0.9	0.93	0.7	0.61	0.86	0.77	0.93
% Solar Parks	2015-2025	0.71	0.64	0.51	0.85	0.78	0.56	0.86	0.64	0.72	0.81
Demand Scenario	2015-2025	high	Low	high	high	high	high	low	high	high	high
Solar Subsidy (percentage to SMP)	2015	1.14	1.05	1.23	1.25	1.07	1.25	1.06	1.02	1.14	1.14
	2016	1.14	1.05	1.23	1.25	1.07	1.25	1.06	1.02	1.14	1.14
	2017	1.14	1.05	1.23	1.25	1.07	1.25	1.06	1.02	1.14	1.14
	2018	1.14	1.05	1.23	1.25	1.07	1.25	1.06	1.02	1.14	1.14
	2019	1.14	1.05	1.23	1.25	1.07	1.25	1.06	1.02	1.14	1.14
	2020	1.05	1	1.1	1.15	1.07	1.25	1	1	1.14	1.14
	2021	1.05	1	1.1	1.15	1.07	1.15	1	1	1.05	1.05
	2022	1.05	1	1.1	1.15	1.07	1.15	1	1	1.05	1.05
	2023	1.05	1	1.1	1.15	1.07	1.15	1	1	1.05	1.05
	2024	1.05	1	1.1	1.15	1	1.15	1	1	1.05	1.05
2025	1.05	1	1.1	1.15	1	1.15	1	1	1.05	1.05	
Wind onshore subsidy (€/MWh)	2015-2025	59.32	69.24	80.02	54.84	88.80	78.66	52.78	65.97	83.00	71.97

There are two specificities to note on the scenarios' data:

- For the years 2015 and 2016, historical RES generation data was available, so no modelling growth rates were applied for these years (this explains the unit growth rates presented in Tables 1 and 2 for those years).
- The subsidies for solar PV are modelled as a percentage of the SMP, which is gradually decreasing every few years in the medium-term scenarios, depicting the decrease trend of the Greek feed-in tariffs. In the short-term scenarios no decrease in the solar subsidy was assumed.

These formed the input data for BSAM to model the operation of the electricity market. The data chosen as outputs (monthly resolution) are as follows:

- The contribution of onshore wind to the electricity mix
- The contribution of solar PV to the electricity mix
- The contribution of imported electricity to the electricity mix (we assume no electricity exports)
- The mean monthly SMP
- The mean monthly total electricity cost² considering the subsidies given to RES

Table 3 presents the format of the BSAM outputs. Since the output data are very extent in each scenario (72x5 and 132x5 matrices for each short-term and medium-term scenario respectively), Table 3 is only a selection from the output matrix for scenario 16 (medium-term).

Table 3 Indicative BSAM outputs

Month	% wind onshore	% solar	% imports	Mean Monthly SMP (€)	Mean Monthly Total Electricity Cost (€)
Jan-15	7.17	3.59	12.60	63.97	64.11
Feb-15	7.86	4.40	7.73	61.87	62.16
Mar-15	6.73	4.94	10.66	55.04	55.80
Apr-15	7.05	9.20	6.26	48.69	50.18
May-15	6.14	9.43	9.46	49.33	50.69
Jun-15	6.41	8.47	4.39	52.28	53.46
Jul-15	6.72	8.00	0.78	57.89	58.82
Aug-15	7.97	7.86	0.35	52.81	54.03

² The total electricity cost is the SMP plus the subsidies given to RES plants divided by the RES produced electricity

Month	% wind onshore	% solar	% imports	Mean Monthly SMP (€)	Mean Monthly Total Electricity Cost (€)
Sep-15	5.95	7.11	5.41	52.24	53.28
Oct-15	9.40	5.85	5.32	49.74	51.23
Nov-15	8.83	5.79	3.76	49.55	51.07
Dec-15	6.46	4.52	1.86	54.37	55.16
:	:	:	:	:	:
Jan-25	9.45	18.37	0.08	36.62	40.03
Feb-25	13.37	29.43	0.11	44.67	50.83
Mar-25	7.96	32.63	5.26	41.55	46.17
Apr-25	6.60	42.29	5.91	38.47	43.65
May-25	8.07	51.31	3.33	36.61	42.70
Jun-25	5.05	44.71	7.42	41.43	46.57
Jul-25	7.06	41.97	5.41	44.61	50.04
Aug-25	5.83	44.84	4.34	46.28	53.15
Sep-25	9.25	37.70	3.36	38.90	43.67
Oct-25	9.18	34.99	4.99	48.10	55.23
Nov-25	9.22	28.22	2.45	42.23	46.66
Dec-25	7.84	22.74	6.22	46.62	50.36

It is important to note that each short-term scenario run by the BSAM required about **2 hours** of execution time, while each medium-term scenario required about **4 hours** of execution time. Following a supervised learning logic³, the 25 scenarios were split into a training set and a test set with 19 and 6 scenarios respectively. The 19 training sets of inputs/outputs were given to STEEM for the calibration process.

3.3.2 Predictive accuracy

After the emulator's calibration, the test set was fed into the emulator to test its predictive accuracy on unknown inputs. In particular, the inputs from the test set were given to STEEM after

³ In supervised machine learning, we use training sets of outputs and inputs to produce an inferred correlation between them. Using the learned correlation, we provide inputs from a test set and compare the learned accuracy against the outputs of the test set.

its training in the previous step, to produce estimations of the outputs. Then, the estimated outputs were compared against those of the test set. For the entire test set, the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the predicted outputs and the test set outputs, for each output parameter, was calculated. The results, as presented in Table 4, show that the MSE value for all parameters is very small, meaning that there is little deviation between the estimated values and the BSAM outputs. Zero MSE would mean perfect matching between estimations and BSAM outputs, however, since STEEM is a statistical framework, some deviation is unavoidable. MSE is not an absolute accuracy metric, however it stands as a useful comparison tool for statistical estimations (i.e. for comparing emulations of different models).

Table 4 Mean squared error of the STEEM predictive results

Output Parameter	P1: % wind onshore	P2: % solar	P3: % imports	P4: Mean Monthly SMP (€)	P5: Mean Monthly Total Electricity Cost (€)
MSE	0.00082572	0.01136342	0.00136864	0.00412089	0.00541309

STEEM's accuracy is also graphically presented in figures 1 and 2, which make a comparative representation of the predicted and test results for each output parameter for two random simulation years, the year 2016 of the 1st test scenario and the year 2019 of the 2nd test scenario. The vertical axis of these graphs shows the normalized values⁴ of the output parameters and the horizontal axis the simulation month of the modelled year.

Figure 1 Comparison of test and predicted results for the year 2016 of the 1st test scenario

⁴ Machine learning algorithms operate more accurately with normalised values.

Figure 2 Comparison of test and predicted results for the year 2019 of the 2nd test scenario

From these results, it can be verified that the test set's output parameter trend is correctly predicted by the emulator. More importantly, the estimation of results required only **0.2 seconds** of execution time per 10-year scenario, while the per 10-year scenario execution time in the BSAM was **4 hours**. These two observations reveal the capabilities of the STEEM to produce quick and accurate simulation results.

3.4 Using STEEM for adaptive policy design

This section presents a methodology to use STEEM as a toolbox to produce adaptive policy pathways. The methodology builds upon Haasnoot et.al (2013) who describe a robust framework - called Dynamic Adaptive Policy Pathways - to facilitate planning and decision making under uncertainty. In the context of TRANSrisk, this framework has been adapted to serve the scope of the project and is hereon analytically described for the Greek case study exploring sustainable RES uptake scenarios.

3.4.1 Step 1 - Problem definition

The first step consists of defining the problem, the scope of analysis (i.e. RES uptake), the description of the objectives (i.e. RES targets), the description of current situation (i.e. Greek energy market context) and the identification of any uncertainties that are considered to complicate or jeopardise the achievement of the targets. In modelling terms, this is the development of an analytical model that simulates future energy transition scenarios. For the

Greek case study such a model is BSAM. The BSAM, as already mentioned, involves input parameters that are vulnerable to uncertainty in the assumptions used. This is common in most forward-looking models, because they require input values for parameters, the future development of which is unknown. Imprecision of these parameters determines the various forms of uncertainty, being present and affecting the nature of modelling outputs. It is important to note that the choice of modelled input parameters should be made in a systematic way using a robust methodology, such as the one described in (Flamos, 2016). This is to assure that these parameters are within the power (or influence) of interested parties to alter, otherwise the entire exercise becomes irrelevant.

3.4.2 Step 2 - Data acquisition and STEEM calibration

In this step, the analytical model prepared in step 1 is run. During the simulations, policy actions (i.e. modelling parameters) are kept constant for the entire modelling period, depicting a situation where the introduction of a policy instrument is kept unchanged for all modelling years. This does not mean that parameter values are static as the modelling years pass, but rather that if some input parameter causes deviation from the predefined targets, it is not changed. The aim of keeping variables constant is to compare the modelling outputs with the set targets, and identify potential vulnerabilities and opportunities from the implementation of the policy. In case historical data (or any other verified sets of inputs and outputs) are available, the first step can be omitted, and any model runs are not required.

The available sets of inputs-outputs are given to the emulator for the calibration phase as described in section 3.3.1. In particular for the Greek case study, input parameters are the ones presented in Table 1 and Table 2 concerning RES growth rates, electricity imports availability, demand scenarios and RES subsidies development. The output parameters, as presented in Table 3 concern electricity mix percentages and electricity costs development. By the above parameter combinations, it is natural to consider only RES subsidies and (implicitly) RES growth rates to be controllable by the policymakers, since they can be guided by installation support measures. On the other hand, imports availability is an unpredictable and uncontrollable factor that is incorporated to stress test the robustness (deviation margins) of the explored policies.

3.4.3 Step 3 - Scenario development and STEEM runs

In step 3, a large number of scenarios, to be emulated by STEEM, are created using the outputs of step 2. The modelling outputs from the analytical models can differ significantly from the set targets, either positively or negatively. Since the scenario runs in the analytical models are few, we can manually check the input parameter values which led to the greatest deviations and use these values as lower and upper bounds to create many random parameter combinations - the scenarios to be run by STEEM. The aim is to model as many parameter combinations as possible, to identify potential opportunities and vulnerabilities that would otherwise be neglected (since analytical models are too resource intensive to simulate many scenarios, most of the time only

scenarios that are based on expert knowledge are simulated, while low-probability scenarios, for example, are usually excluded).

3.4.4 Step 4 - Identification of trigger points

In this step, a “cause and effect” analysis is performed to identify triggers (Haasnoot, Kwakkel, Walker, & ter Maat, 2013) that signpost imminent deviation from the desired outputs (policy outcomes), outputs with high risk, or policy opportunities that stakeholders can consider when designing policies. This is done by utilising a clustering algorithm called Patient Rule Induction Method (PRIM). The PRIM algorithm can identify segments of the input set that correspond to answers with similar characteristics. As such, one can identify the parameters that led to success or failure of a specific policy instrument. The algorithm is analytically described in TRANSrisk Deliverable 6.3 (Taylor, Papadelis, Wanjiru, van Vliet, & Lieu, 2017). The process of identifying trigger points is as follows:

- Using the PRIM algorithm, we identify scenario outputs (i.e. policy outputs) in the end of the simulation period that exceed the outcome deviation threshold.
- For the set of scenarios that resulted in failure/high risk, we go back early enough in time (i.e. to the half of the simulation time) and with the same criterion (end of simulation output threshold) we apply PRIM to identify segments of the input space (combination of controllable and uncontrollable variables) with similarities at that simulation point. The values contained in these segments are trigger points, because they inform us that a combination of input variables lying in this segment will probably lead to failure.

Accordingly, the same algorithm can be used to identify opportunistic trigger points.

3.4.5 Step 5 - Design of adaptive policies

This step is reverse to step 4. We move forward in time until a trigger point is encountered. This informs us that beyond that timeframe a policy will not have the desired results (policy “sell-by date), and some change is needed to prevent failure (adaptation tipping point). The process of adaptive policy design with the aid of the previous steps goes on as follows:

- (iii) We choose a policy (combination of inputs) that is preferred according to stakeholders’ perspectives (i.e. maximum effectiveness, policy integration etc.) for the studied case.
- (iv) We go forward in time until we encounter a trigger point. At that point we are informed that the policy will probably reach its “sell-by” date so a different plan needs to be implemented. As such an alternative policy from the available policy ensemble is chosen.
- (v) We continue moving forward in time checking for triggers until the end of simulation time is reached.

- (vi) At this point, the result is an adaptation pathway map. This is a scenario map with adaptation tipping points, showing different pathways to reach the desired policy outcome, depending on the starting point and the choice of adaptation tipping points.
- (vii) Depending on the perspective of the policy designer, the appropriate pathway/pathways are chosen from the adaptation pathway map.
- (viii) Continuous real-time monitoring should be in place to identify system distortions. In case this occurs, new data should be available and iterations between steps 2,3,4 and 5 should be made to identify new pathways, avoid vulnerabilities and take advantage of opportunities.

3.4.6 Results from the Greek case study

The above methodology has been used for the 6 test scenarios in the Greek case study to produce a scenario adaptation pathway map. Policymakers are provided with a map that shows 2019-2025 pathways for RES subsidies and RES penetration that keep the SMP between 47.5-51 €/MWh. It should be noted that the values of the input parameters are only a computational experiment, generated by a random scenario generator, to check the accuracy and efficiency of the emulator (annually changing RES targets are not realistic). Furthermore, the use of STEEM is only supportive to the design of adaptive policies. This means that STEEM's results do not suggest optimal strategies, rather than help visualise aspects that stakeholders could omit during the policy design process. The adaptation map that was produced is shown in Figure 3. This adaptation map shows which scenarios (policies - vertical axis) keep the SMP between the specified margins in each simulation year (horizontal axis).

Figure 3 Greek case study adaptation map

As it can be seen, there are multiple ways to maintain the SMP within the set limits. The strategy to be followed depends on the stakeholders' perspectives. Here we present two perspectives: (i) the lowest SMP between the set limits should guide policy options and (ii) minimum policy changes

until 2025 should guide policy options. For the second case, two pathways were available, so the lowest 2025 SMP was set as an extra criterion. Each scenario's parameter values are available to the user in table forms, similar to the BSAM outputs as presented in table 3 in section 3.3.1. Adding each of those criteria to the full adaptation map results in the adaptation maps presented in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Figure 4 Lowest SMP strategy

Figure 5 Minimum policy changes strategy

Now that the desired adaptive policy pathways have been generated, it is time to structure the input parameters' sequence (policy options), that lead us to the desired results. As described in section 3.4.4, the PRIM algorithm can identify segments of the input space that correspond to

answers with similar characteristics. As such, since we have identified the desired pathways, we can also identify the respective inputs that lead to the desired results. The respective policy actions (inputs) that should be implemented to achieve these two scenarios are presented in the following tables:

Table 5 Policy inputs for the lowest SMP strategy

	Solar PV subsidy (% of SMP)	Wind Subsidy (€/MWh)	Solar PV growth target (% relative to 2016 values)	Wind growth target (% relative to 2016 values)
2019	1.06	52.78	2.88	1.14
2020	1.00	52.78	3.52	1.23
2021	1.00	65.97	4.2	1.26
2022	1.00	65.97	5.05	1.33
2023	1.05	71.97	6.1	1.37
2024	1.15	54.84	6.1	1.37
2025	1.15	54.84	6.15	1.37

Table 6 Policy inputs for the minimum policy changes strategy

	Solar PV subsidy (% of SMP)	Wind Subsidy (€/MWh)	Solar PV growth target (% relative to 2016 values)	Wind growth target (% relative to 2016 values)
2019	1.06	52.78	2.88	1.14
2020	1.00	52.78	3.52	1.23
2021	1.15	54.84	3.52	1.23
2022	1.15	54.84	3.67	1.23
2023	1.15	54.84	3.93	1.23
2024	1.15	54.84	4.83	1.23
2025	1.15	54.84	6.15	1.27

Comparing the two pathway perspectives, we can see that in the “lowest SMP” strategy, several retroactive changes in RES subsidies occur and high RES penetration targets are required early on. This could be problematic for a country in recession, such as Greece. Retroactive changes in RES subsidies do not favour RES investments and the high RES targets may not be achieved. Furthermore, high penetration levels in the early years require a high level of financial support, which may be difficult considering the current financial climate in Greece.

On the other hand, the “minimum policy changes” strategy shows steady and attractive RES subsidies throughout the simulations years - an observation that could attract investments. Furthermore, the RES penetration targets are not too “steep” meaning that, with steady steps, we could have high expectations for Greece to achieve them. As such, the “minimum policy changes” strategy seems to be more suitable for the case of Greece.

3.5 Emulation Functional Principles

As stated in Deliverable 6.3, emulators are statistical approximations of analytical models (Taylor, Papadelis, Wanjiru, van Vliet, & Lieu, 2017). They can approximate model results for sets of inputs that have not been simulated by the analytical models in much less time. As such, they constitute an appropriate tool to use, whenever multiple “what-if” scenarios need to be investigated (Erickson, Ankenman, & Sanchez, 2018). Furthermore, their stochastic nature enables them to quantify model uncertainty and its relevance to the simulation outcomes (Taylor, Papadelis, Wanjiru, van Vliet, & Lieu, 2017). This is based on the fact that predictions are not provided in the form of fixed points, but rather in the form of a distribution with an expected value (mean) and a confidence level (variance) (Yoon & Moon, 2018). A detailed description of GP-based emulators, like STEEM, has been presented in Deliverable 6.3 (Taylor, Papadelis, Wanjiru, van Vliet, & Lieu, 2017), however for consistency reasons, we mention some basic principles in this section too.

The aim is to approximate the results $f(x_i)$ of a model, given a set of inputs x_i , which have not been evaluated in the original model. By $f(\cdot)$ we denote the latent model formulae, which the emulator does not need to know. We assume that the modelled data (inputs and outputs) follow a Gaussian distribution with mean $m_f(x_i)$ and variance $\sigma_f^2(x_i)$, and also that a change in a specific value affects other values as well, reflecting covariance between model’s variables. This allows us to assume that the modelled data follow a joint Gaussian distribution specified as:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{bmatrix} f(x_1) \\ f(x_2) \\ \vdots \\ f(x_n) \end{bmatrix} \sim N \left(\begin{bmatrix} f(x_1) \\ f(x_2) \\ \vdots \\ f(x_n) \end{bmatrix} \mid \begin{bmatrix} m_f(x_1) \\ m_f(x_2) \\ \vdots \\ m_f(x_n) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} k_f(x_1, x_1) & k_f(x_1, x_2) & \cdots & k_f(x_1, x_n) \\ k_f(x_2, x_1) & k_f(x_2, x_2) & \cdots & k_f(x_2, x_n) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ k_f(x_n, x_1) & k_f(x_n, x_2) & \cdots & k_f(x_n, x_n) \end{bmatrix} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $k_f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}^*)$ is the chosen covariance (kernel) function (STEEM uses the Matérn 3/2 kernel). An infinite number of random variables, as denoted in the above formula, any finite number of which follows a joint Gaussian distribution, is a GP (Rasmussen & Williams, 2006). Formula (1) is the prior distribution of the GP - our assumption of the function space on which the model data lie, without considering the actual data we have.

Conditioning of the prior GP distribution on the modelled data $\mathbf{D} = \{(x_i, f(x_i)), i = 1, \dots, n\}$ is done using the following formula:

$$p(f|\mathbf{D}) = N\left(K_{ff}(K_{ff} + \sigma_\varepsilon^2 I)^{-1} f(x), K_{ff} - K_{ff}(K_{ff} + \sigma_\varepsilon^2 I)^{-1} K_{ff}\right) \quad (2)$$

where K_{ff} is the covariance matrix, produced by evaluating the kernel function k_f only between the known inputs x_i :

$$K_{ff} = \begin{bmatrix} k_f(x_1, x_1) & k_f(x_1, x_2) & \cdots & k_f(x_1, x_n) \\ k_f(x_2, x_1) & k_f(x_2, x_2) & \cdots & k_f(x_2, x_n) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ k_f(x_n, x_1) & k_f(x_n, x_2) & \cdots & k_f(x_n, x_n) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Conditioning means that we reduce the assumed prior function space to those that are consistent with the observed data. This formula trains our emulator to be used in the next step for estimations.

Now that the emulator is trained, we can approximate model outputs on new inputs X_* using the posterior distribution:

$$p(f_*|\mathbf{D}) = N\left(f_* | m_f(\mathbf{X}_*) + K_{*f} K_{ff}^{-1} (y - m_f(\mathbf{X})), K_{**} - K_{*f} K_{ff}^{-1} K_{f*}\right), \quad (4)$$

where K_{f*} is the covariance matrix, produced by evaluating the kernel function k_f between the known inputs x_i and the unknown inputs x_i^* :

$$K_{f*} = \begin{bmatrix} k_f(x_1, x_1^*) & k_f(x_1, x_2^*) & \cdots & k_f(x_1, x_n^*) \\ k_f(x_2, x_1^*) & k_f(x_2, x_2^*) & \cdots & k_f(x_2, x_n^*) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ k_f(x_n, x_1^*) & k_f(x_n, x_2^*) & \cdots & k_f(x_n, x_n^*) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Accordingly, we calculate the covariance matrices K_{*f} and K_{**} .

Finally, we can evaluate the predictive uncertainty at each input X_* using the following formula:

$$\text{Var}(f|X_*) = K_{**} - K_{*f} K_{ff}^{-1} K_{f*} \quad (6)$$

This equation is probably the most important feature incorporated in STEEM, since it allows us to identify the inputs with the highest level of uncertainty and then reinforce emulator's training set at these points for more accurate results. Additionally, the identification of the most uncertain inputs enables us to identify the uncertain assumptions of the original model, alter them and then

produce more robust policy pathways, by detecting real-life factors leading to policy failures. The following flowchart gives an overview of the GP-based emulation procedure.

Figure 6 GP-based emulation flowchart

4 TOOLBOX FOR MITIGATION POLICY PATHWAYS USING THE MEMO (MACROECONOMIC MITIGATIONS OPTIONS) MODEL

4.1 Introduction

The toolbox for mitigation policy pathways is a web application which allows non-experts to conduct simulations of various policies using the macroeconomic MEMO (MacroEconomic Mitigations Options) model. MEMO, developed at the Institute for Structural Research, is a large-scale Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium model. It has been successfully used to analyse the macroeconomic implications of various policies relating to climate change, energy sector, taxes, resource use, etc. within several national and international studies.

Operating such a model presents a significant barrier of entry for non-experts, as it usually requires advanced programming and technical skills. The toolbox enables policy makers and analysts, who are not experts in quantitative economics, to run macroeconomic simulations. We are convinced that, when the process is automated, successfully conducting and interpreting results of macroeconomic simulations can be carried out by policy makers. It is enough to become familiar with the general principles governing the model, its basic structure and the interpretation and format of the input data to be simulated. These elements are provided in a concise form in this tutorial. 4.2 provides an overview of the toolbox, whilst 4.3 details the type of simulations that can be carried out. 4.4 shows the practical application of the toolbox to the TRANSrisk Poland case study. 4.5 describes the technical details of the model.

4.2 Toolbox overview

The toolbox incorporates three country-level MEMO models calibrated for Chile, Greece and Poland. It contains several predefined simulation types, requiring the end-user to provide only input data. Simulation types include:

- Environmental taxes
- Direct expansion plans and investments in the energy sector, investments and mitigation actions in remaining sectors and the household
- Sequencing simulations linking investments in the energy sector with environmental taxes
- Optimisation simulations

The main features of the MEMO model are:

- Production structure, including labour, capital energy and materials (intermediate use) as factors of production (according to KLEMS⁵ approach)
- A multisector production structure calibrated directly to input/output (IO) matrices, endogenous technological choice, various frictions, an elaborate labour market using the search mechanism
- Open economy, government sector and accounts for greenhouse gas emissions

These elements of the model allow it to realistically simulate the effect of various interventions related to climate change mitigation on a range of macroeconomic indicators such as gross domestic product, value added, employment, unemployment, wages, exports, imports, tax revenue and others on an aggregate and sector level. This report is divided into several sections. In the first, we provide a description of the application and the graphical user interface, whereas the second section provides examples on how the simulations can be used in practice. The final section provides a semi-technical outline of the model with basic equations, general structure, calibration and simulation procedure.

The application is available online at the webpage <https://transrisk.ibs.org.pl/>. After registering and signing in with an email and password, the user is taken to the main menu of the application, which is shown in Figure 7. The only data that we collect is the email address used to register and input data for simulations. In the top right corner of the application is the “*Your account*” menu. Under this menu the users have the option to change their password, manage their profile, open the tutorial for the application and sign out. An important option in the “*profile*” submenu is to change the language of the application. The starting language is by default English, but the user has also the option to switch to Polish or Spanish.

Figure 7 Main menu of the application

Running simulations is managed through the “*Country*” and “*Simulation type*” menus. In order to run a simulation, the user must select one of the three country models and one of the four simulation types. After this selection has been made, the user must click the “+” icon and a popup window will appear, where the user can create a scenario for the country-simulation combination

⁵ <http://www.euklems.net/>

and give it a name, e.g. “CHILE TAX”. After introducing data and running simulations, the data will be stored in the scenario, allowing the user to load it for work during subsequent sessions.

Figure 8 Inputting intervention (scenario) data

Upon opening a scenario two tabs appear with “*Scenario variables*” and “*Result variables*”, along with the main table located in the centre for setting input data for the years 2018-2050, as can be seen in Figure 8. The first of these tabs holds the variables defining the interventions (scenarios) that can be simulated. The user can then select a subset of these and, after they appear in the main table, she can input data for them manually or copy them from a spreadsheet. If the data has been incorrectly inputted, the user can reset the data to the default zero values by clicking “*Reset values*”. Conducting simulations is done by clicking the “*Calculate scenario*” button. The user is then automatically moved to the second tab, which shows the result of the simulation. These variables are divided into the following groups:

- Main macroeconomic variables
- Environmental variables
- Gross domestic product in sectors
- Employment in sectors
- Wages in sectors
- Investment in sectors
- Capital stock in sectors

- CO₂ emissions in sectors
- Environmental taxes

When analysing the result of a simulation, one must keep in mind that MEMO is a macroeconomic model, in which the energy sector is not modelled in such detail as in bottom up energy system models. The main aim of the model is to shed light on possible developments in the general economy (top-down approach). Therefore, the results for the environmental variables, such as energy use from intermittent and non-intermittent sources and materials use, should be interpreted as a rough estimate. The environmental taxes result variables should be analysed when one is running the optimisation simulations, in order to check the resulting tax rate. In case of running environmental tax simulations, the result will simply be the tax rates that were provided as input.

To view the result of a group of variables, or a particular variable, the user must select a folder (or expand it) and select single variables. The results appear as time series in the main table, with variables affected highlighted in yellow. The user can now select variables from the main table and draw a graph for them by right-clicking in the main table and selecting “*Draw graph*”. Results can also be exported to a spreadsheet using the “*Export to Excel*” button. The application only supports basic graph drawing and we recommend conducting an in-depth analysis of the results in a separate spreadsheet program.

The simulations are conducted using a Kalman filter numerical procedure which provides the values of shock variables corresponding to the intervention variables. All results are shown as percent deviations from the steady state of the model. The steady state of the model should be interpreted as the business as usual (non-intervention) scenario for the main macroeconomic variables such as GDP, employment etc. up to the year 2050. The set of result variables for the Environmental taxes, Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)/Operational Expenditure (OPEX) simulations and sequencing simulations is the same. Results for the optimisation simulations are shown in a different format. Since the model is solved using a linear approximation around the steady state, the deviations from the steady state should not be excessively large for the results to be feasible. As a rule of thumb, we encourage to use and interpret results for which this deviation is not larger than 50% for any variable.

Figure 9 Sample simulation results

4.3 Simulations

In this section we describe the predefined simulation types that the user can run using the toolbox. The simulations are divided into the following four groups:

- (i) Environmental tax simulations
- (ii) CAPEX and OPEX simulations
- (iii) Sequential simulations
- (iv) Optimisation simulations

4.3.1 Tax simulations

This group encompasses the simplest and most straightforward types of simulations: environmental taxes and subsidies. The taxes that the application supports are:

- CO₂ emissions tax. The user can set an economy-wide CO₂ tax, or can chose to place a tax on one of the following groups of sectors: Agriculture, Mining and Quarrying, Manufacturing Industry, Electricity Generation, Construction Industry, Transport and Service sector. The rate

for the tax rates is USD per ton of CO₂ emissions⁶ and the application calculates these tax rates into model units automatically.

- Excise tax on the sale of coal, crude oil, gas, refined petroleum products and electricity. The rate of the tax is defined as USD per relevant quantity of given product.
- Subsidy for the use of renewable energy sources. The rate of this subsidy is given as a percentage of the price.

The user may choose to simulate any number of taxes and subsidies simultaneously. When doing so, it is important to remember that the CO₂ tax rates are additive. For example, setting the economy-wide CO₂ tax to 10 USD per ton and the Transport sector CO₂ tax to 10 USD per ton will result in a simulation, where the Transport sector is taxed at 20 USD per ton, and remaining sectors are taxed at the rate of 10 USD per ton. In the model we assume that the tax revenue is transferred to the household, and that the subsidy is financed by a reduction in transfers to the household (or equivalently in the form of a lump sum tax).

4.3.2 CAPEX and OPEX simulations

This simulation type assesses the macroeconomic consequences of interventions in the energy sector, such as large-scale investment in renewables and the phase-out of fossil fuels. The input data needed for this simulation is:

- Investment for new scenario relative to business as usual scenario in millions of the given currency
- Percent change in the energy price relative to the business as usual scenario
- Change in the expenditure on coal consumption relative to the business as usual scenario in millions of the given currency
- Change in the expenditure on oil and gas use relative to the business as usual scenario in millions of the given currency

The input data for this simulation should ideally come from a bottom-up energy system model which calculates the necessary investment and changes in fuel consumption for various scenarios for the energy system. To compare the differences in the macroeconomic effects of various energy system scenarios, one should define a baseline (e.g. business as usual scenario involving continued fossil fuel use) and the alternative scenario (e.g. switch to renewable energy sources). The input data should then be calculated as differences between an alternative scenario and the baseline.

The simulations for remaining sector and household interventions require the user to provide data on the required investment and the resulting change in the use of materials, disaggregated

⁶ Only CO₂ emissions, not CO₂-equivalent emissions of other GHG emissions.

between all the sectors of the economy. For each sector, there is a total of 15 time series for the user to provide data for, however typical simulations will involve inputting data for only a small subset. For example, if one is interested in assessing the effects of a thermal insulation program for the household, it is enough to provide data on the amount of required investment and the change in the use of coal, gas, oil and electricity. Likewise, if the mitigation action involves investment in electric vehicles or more fuel-efficient vehicles, then the user should provide the change in the use of refined petroleum products and electricity, and the required investment.

4.3.3 Sequencing simulations

The structure of the sequencing simulations are similar to the CAPEX and OPEX simulations, however the underlying economic question answered is different. In these simulations, the policy maker is interested in the interrelation between a fixed investment plan for the energy sector and a carbon tax on the entire economy, which is placed after the investment plan has been set in motion. In this simulation the user inputs the same data as for the CAPEX/OPEX simulation and additionally defines a target drop in CO₂ emissions. The additional carbon tax necessary to bring CO₂ emissions to the desired level is calculated endogenously as part of the simulation.

4.3.4 Optimisation simulations

These simulations allow for the study of the optimal level and type of taxation of the economy. In this simulation the user selects several environmental taxes that they wish to examine, and define a desired drop in CO₂ emissions for the years 2030 and 2050 (note that the drop should be set as a negative number). The application then separately calculates the necessary rates for each of the taxes necessary to achieve the drop in CO₂, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Setting optimisation simulations

The user can then compare the results of each tax on selected main macroeconomic variables and learn which of these has the smallest negative impact, as shown in Figure 11. For the sample simulation shown here, the economy wide CO₂ tax has the smallest negative impact on GDP.

Figure 11 Analysing the result of optimisation simulations

4.4 Sample simulation

In this subsection we show in detail how a sample CAPEX and OPEX simulation for the energy system was prepared for Poland as part of the TRANSrisk project. We first discuss how the input

data was prepared using a bottom-up energy system model, how this model is soft-linked to the MEMO model and then we briefly analyse the results.

The input data for developments in the electricity generation sector is prepared using the Model of Optimal Energy Mix for Poland (MOEM), which was developed by the Department of Strategic Analysis within The Chancellery of the Prime Minister. The MOEM model is a central planner least cost linear optimisation model. It takes the current energy system and provides an investment plan into new power plants and the generation structure for the time horizon up to the year 2060 that satisfies the projected path of electricity demand. The model considers the entire cost structure, namely that of installing new capacity, fuel, maintenance, EU ETS prices and other operational costs and a range of additional exogenous constraints such as maximum allowed emissions or minimum installed renewable energy source capacity.

Using this model, we create two possible scenarios for the electricity generation system. We feed the input data into the model: electricity demand, assumptions regarding costs of technologies from 2017 Annual Technological Baseline by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory, EU ETS price increasing up to 80 USD per ton in the year 2050. For the first scenario, which we will refer to as the baseline scenario we assume no additional constraints on the energy mix. For the second scenario, which we will refer to as the decarbonisation scenario we assume an additional constraint that CO₂ emissions must be reduced by 60% relative to the 2018 level. The output of the MOEM model is the path of capital expenditure that the least cost energy system requires in each of the scenarios, the change in the expenditure on resources and the change in the cost of generating electricity. This is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operational expenditure (OPEX) required by the energy system in the baseline and decarbonisation scenarios

The input data for the MEMO model is calculated as the difference between the scenario pathways for capital, gas and coal and prices. To account for the difference in remaining costs between

scenarios, we calculate the percent difference in total yearly costs for the two scenarios. These four time series are then used as input for the MEMO model, as can be seen in Figure 13.

Figure 13 Inputting data for the CAPEX OPEX simulation for Poland

The monetary values that the user provides are translated into shares of GDP using the baseline for this value which is encoded in the application. Now it is enough to click the “*Calculate scenario*” button to run the simulation and analyse the results. One can then select main macroeconomic variables and analyse the impact upon them. The main stand out result is the increase in total investment in the economy, which is due to the increased investment in the energy sector. However, this increase crowds out investment in other sectors of the economy; this contributes to a slight fall in GDP and employment, and a much larger decrease of private consumption. These results are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14 Analysing the results for main macroeconomic variables for CAPEX OPEX simulation for Poland

It is also informative to study the sector developments that result from the intervention, in particular for employment. These results for selected sectors are shown in Figure 15. First of all, employment in the mining and quarrying sector is significantly reduced. When interpreting this and other results, it is important to keep in mind that this is an additional change in employment with respect to the business as usual scenario in which this intervention does not take place. While we do not specify a BAU scenario for Poland, all projections for employment in the mining sector in Poland show a decrease, and the change simulated by the model is an additional decrease. This is a direct result of the fact that the electricity sector intervention is linked to a decrease in the use of coal, much of which is produced domestically in Poland. The second picture shows the results for employment in the construction sector, which increased by approximately 1 percent. A close inspection of the IO matrix for Poland (or for any other country for that matter) would shed light on the reason for such developments.

Construction sector output is one of the main elements of the aggregate investment good, and the electricity sector intervention is linked to an increase in demand for capital. The final picture shows the result for the public services sector. This sector is not affected directly and most of the product is purchased by the government which operates a rather stable fiscal rule. Employment in the public sector is only affected slightly through the general equilibrium effect due to the intermediate use structure. Altogether, the impact on employment here is negligible.

Figure 15 Analysing the results for sector employment for CAPEX OPEX simulation for Poland

4.5 Model outline

In this section we discuss the basic structure and features of the MEMO model, concentrating on its aspects which are crucial for understanding and interpreting results of the simulations. The number of equations presented here is limited in order to not burden the reader with difficult technical matters. It is important to note that the three country models for Chile, Greece and Poland share the same mathematical structure of all equations, with the difference between the models stemming from different country-specific parameterisations. Readers interested in a

detailed technical description of the model are referred to the IBS research report by Antosiewicz and Kowal (2016), which is available online.

Figure 16 Main building blocks of the model and their connections

The main agents represented in the model are the household, firms (divided into sectors of the economy), government and the foreign sector (which represents the rest of the world from the point of view of a particular country). The decision rules of particular agents are based upon the optimisation of an ‘intertemporal’ utility or profit function: agents consider not only the present state of the economy but also expectations about the future. The agents of the model interact with each other on markets, where relative prices are established, and exchange is conducted. For example, the household offers labour to firms in exchange for wages on the labour market, whilst also purchasing consumption goods from firms on the goods market. The government collects several taxes from the household and firms, and uses its revenue to finance public consumption and transfers. These and other connections between model agents are shown in Figure 16.

4.5.1 Household

The household seeks to maximize utility from consumption, which is given by:

$$\max_{C_t} E_0 \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \beta^t u(C_t), \quad (7)$$

where β is the subjective discount factor, $u(C_t)$ is a concave utility function of consumption C_t , and E_0 denotes the expectations operator, which signifies that the household does not know the future but only makes decisions based on expectations about it. The household budget constraint consists of expenditures on the consumption good, taxes paid to the government at rate τ_X , investments in assets A_t and cost of searching for a job Ξ_t . The income side includes wage income $W_t N_t$, income from asset holdings A_{t-1} which generate income given by the rate r_t , dividends from firms Π_t and transfers from the government T_t . This is encapsulated in the budget constraint equation:

$$(1 + \tau_{VAT})P_t^C C_t + A_t + \Xi_t = W_t N_t (1 - \tau_W) + (1 - \tau_D)\Pi_t + T_t + A_{t-1}(1 + r_{t-1}) \quad (8)$$

In each period, the household decides how much effort its unemployed members spend on searching for a job, which is reflected in the monetary cost Ξ_t . Unemployed job seekers are matched with vacancies posted on the labour market and may become employed. The fraction of employed population is denoted by N_t . The details of the labour market are presented in the section devoted to the firm.

4.5.2 Firm

In the MEMO model firms are divided into 14 sectors denoted by the set S . For each sector $s \in S$ there is a representative firm which maximises its expected stream of profits discounted by the discount factor Λ_t :

$$\max_{INV_t^s, N_t^s, \dots} E_0 \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \Lambda_t \Pi_t^s, \quad (9)$$

Each firm operates a multi-stage production function using as input capital, labour, energy and intermediate use materials from other sectors. In the first stage capital K_t^s and energy ENG_t^s is combined to produce the composite KE_t^s using a constant elasticity of substitution (CES) production function with share parameter θ_E^s and elasticity parameter ϵ_E^s .

$$KE_t^s = \left[(1 - \theta_E^s)(K_t^s)^{\frac{\epsilon_E^s - 1}{\epsilon_E^s}} + \theta_E^s (ENG_t^s)^{\frac{\epsilon_E^s - 1}{\epsilon_E^s}} \right]^{\frac{\epsilon_E^s}{\epsilon_E^s - 1}} \quad (10)$$

In the second stage this composite is combined with labour N_t^s to arrive at the subsequent composite product KLE_t^s also using a CES function:

$$KLE_t^s = \left[\theta_{KE}^s (KE_t^s)^{\frac{\epsilon_{KE}^s - 1}{\epsilon_{KE}^s}} + (1 - \theta_{KE}^s) (N_t^s)^{\frac{\epsilon_{KE}^s - 1}{\epsilon_{KE}^s}} \right]^{\frac{\epsilon_{KE}^s}{\epsilon_{KE}^s - 1}} \quad (11)$$

In the final stage it is linked with materials M_t^s to produce the final sector good Y_t^s :

$$Y_t^s = \left[(1 - \theta_M^s) (KLE_t^s)^{\frac{\epsilon_M^s - 1}{\epsilon_M^s}} + \theta_M^s (M_t^s)^{\frac{\epsilon_M^s - 1}{\epsilon_M^s}} \right]^{\frac{\epsilon_M^s}{\epsilon_M^s - 1}} \quad (12)$$

The materials input M_t^s for each sector s is composed of materials coming from all sectors except energy (which as described above is treated as a separate input).

$$M_t^s = f(M_t^{s,u}), u \in S \quad (13)$$

We model the material M_t^s input assuming substitution (through a CES function) between fuels $s \in S_F$ and remaining non-fuel materials $s \in S_{NF}$, and perfect complementarity between non-fuel materials (through a Leontief production function). We assume that the set of fuels in the model is the following: coal, oil, gas and refined petroleum products. Finally, we assume that each material input $M_t^{s,u}$ is a CES composite of domestically produced $M_t^{s,u,H}$ and imported $M_t^{s,u,F}$ input, thus considering foreign trade. The final product of each firm is divided according to the final use part of the IO matrix and sold to the (i) household and (ii) government for private and public consumption, (iii) to other firms as investment (iv) exported or (v) as materials to other sectors according to the intermediate use part of the IO matrix.

In order to secure the necessary capital and labour for the production process, firms make investment decisions and post job vacancies. Vacancies are matched with unemployed job seekers on the labour market according to the search and matching. The model is therefore particularly useful for studying the short and medium-term effects of climate policies on the labour market.

CO₂ emissions are modelled at the firm and household levels, and are a function of the amount of fuel materials used. Parameters $\theta_{CO_2}^{s,u}$ are used to calibrate the emissions in sectors to values observed in the data.

$$CO2_t^s = \sum_{u \in S_F} \theta_{CO2}^{s,u} M_t^{s,u}, s \in S \cup \{Household\} \quad (14)$$

4.5.3 Government

In the model we assume that the government collects three main taxes: personal income (wage) tax, value added tax and a dividend tax. Furthermore, it can levy various environmental taxes, such as a CO₂ tax and excise tax on fuels. The size of these taxes is set by the user during the simulations. We assume that the government spends revenue on the purchase of public consumption and on transfers. It is crucial to note that we assume a closure of the government budget through the transfer to the household. This contrasts to other possible uses of the tax revenue such as reducing labour taxation or introducing various green subsidies, which has been advocated by environmentalists and economists alike. The rationale behind this choice is that in the simulations we wish to show the macroeconomic distortionary effect caused by a single environmental tax only. Combining an environmental tax with another distortionary mechanism would impede the analysis of the tax alone. Furthermore, while in reality the green tax revenue might be spent on more productive goals, this would require a completely new study.

4.5.4 Calibration

To calibrate the model for each of the countries we use several data sources. The most important element of the models is the sector structure which is calibrated to an IO matrix which distinguishes domestic and imported intermediate use for each sector. Depending on the data source, a typical IO matrix contains data on flows for at least 40 sectors, while for computational reasons a Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium (DSGE) model can accommodate up to 20 sectors. Constructing the model therefore requires the aggregation of sectors which are not crucial from the point of view of the analysis, whilst distinguishing the ones which are important. In our analysis, private services can be aggregated into a single sector (except for transport, which is carbon intensive) without harm to the environmental aspect of the model. On the other hand, the manufacturing industry sector should be disaggregated into those sections based on their carbon intensity, as this will give a more detailed view of the impact of interventions. Finally, since the model is mainly used for the analysis of the electricity production sector, we make a detailed disaggregation of it.

The way firms are divided into sectors is shown in Table 7. The structure of the model is based on Eurostat IO matrices according to the Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community NACE, Rev. 2 for Greece and Poland, whereas for the Chilean model we use IO matrices from the Structural Analysis Database. A basic symmetric structure of the model has been altered in two ways. First of all, we assume that the Mining and Quarrying sector produces several distinct goods which are crucial from the point of view of climate policy: coal, oil gas and 'other'. Second, we assume that there are four distinct sectors responsible for the production of

electricity: a) coal and lignite, b) remaining fossil fuels (mainly gas and oil), c) intermittent renewable energy (wind and PV) and d) non-intermittent renewable energy (mainly biomass and hydro). The disaggregation into these four sectors was conducted using data on the structure of installed capacity and electricity generation from International Energy Agency.

Data for sector employment, unemployment and government revenue with respect to different taxes was taken from the OECD database for all countries in order to ensure consistency. Sector CO₂ emissions were calibrated using data from International Energy Agency.

Table 7 Sector Structure of the model

Sector name	NACE sections
Agriculture	A01-A03
Mining and quarrying (which produces following products: coal, oil, gas and other)	B05-B09 (coal: B05, oil: B061, gas: B062, other: B07-B09)
Light Manufacturing Industry	C10-C16
Energy Intensive Manufacturing Industry	C17,C18,C20, C22-C24
Advanced Manufacturing Industry	C21, C25-C33
Refined Petroleum Products Manufacturing Industry	C19
Coal Electricity Production	Subset of D35
Remaining Fossil Fuel Electricity Production	Subset of D35
Intermittent Renewable Electricity Production	Subset of D35
Nonintermittent Renewable Electricity Production	Subset of D35
Construction Industry	F41-F43

Sector name	NACE sections
Transport	H49-H53
Market Services	E36-E39,G45-G47,I55-N82,R90-U99
Public Services	O84-Q88

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